

MATERIALS OF ZINC OXIDE NANOPARTICLES AND THEIR POTENTIAL APPLICATIONS: PROGRESS, CHALLENGES AND PERSPECTIVES

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Abstract. Extensive research in nanotechnology has been conducted to elucidate new behaviors and properties of nanoscale materials fully. ZnO nanoparticles (NPs) have gained great importance due to their distinct physical and chemical properties and are, therefore, being extensively studied to exploit these properties.

This study first develops various chemical methods for the preparation of ZnO NPs, namely the mechanochemical process, controlled precipitation, sol-gel method, vapor transport method, solvothermal and hydrothermal methods, and methods using emulsion and microemulsion. In particular, the paper describes green methods of using plant extracts for the synthesis of ZnO NPs. Modifications of ZnO with organic (carboxylic acid, silanes) and inorganic (metal oxide) compounds and polymer matrices are then described.

Many applications of ZnO NPs have been presented in various fields such as the rubber industry, pharmaceutical industry, cosmetics, textile industry, optoelectronics, and agriculture. The photocatalytic and various biomedical applications of ZnO are detailed. Finally, an attempt was made to explore the current challenges and future scope of synthetic methods and applications of ZnO NPs.

Keywords: nanoparticulate zinc oxide, modification, chemical methods, potential applications.

INTRODUCTION

Found in the Earth's crust as the mineral zincite, ZnO appears as a white powder and is almost insoluble in water. Zinc oxide is the second most common metal oxide after iron. It is a cheap and safe metal oxide that is easy to prepare. ZnO powder is used in many materials and products, such as ceramics, glass, cement, rubber, lubricants, paints, ointments, adhesives, plastics, sealants, pigments, food products, batteries, ferrites, and fire retardants. Is widely used as an adjunct. ZnO can adopt three possible polymorphs, rock salt, wurtzite, and zinc blende. The rock salt polymorph exists under high pressure and is therefore extremely rare. At ambient pressure and temperature, ZnO has a hexagonal wurtzite crystal structure with two lattice parameters, a , and c , with values of 0.3296 nm and 0.52065 nm, respectively. In hexagonal wurtzite, O^{2-} ions occupy hexagonal close-packing (hcp) lattice sites, while Zn^{2+} ions occupy alternate tetrahedral holes, in contrast to the zinc-blende structure, where O^{2-} ions occupy cubic close-packing (ccp) creates a row. Zn^{2+} ions occupy tetrahedral spaces. ZnO has a wide band gap of ~ 3.37 eV and a large-exciter binding energy of 60 meV. The physical and chemical behavior of zinc oxide nanoparticles can be easily prepared by changing the morphology using different synthesis routes and different materials [1].

ZnO has many unique chemical and physical properties, i.e., high chemical stability, high electrochemical coupling coefficient, wide radiation absorption, and high photostability, which makes it a key technological material among all metal oxides and enables its wide application. Gives in different fields. Zinc is a component of the pancreatic hormone insulin, while copper is necessary for respiration and photosynthesis. ZnO belongs to group II-VI semiconductors in materials science, as zinc belongs to group 2 and oxygen belongs to group 6 of the periodic table. Its covalency is at the boundary between ionic and covalent semiconductors. It also has good transparency, high electron mobility, large exciton binding energy (60 meV), wide band gap (3.37eV), strong room temperature luminescence, high thermal and mechanical stability at room temperature, has a wide absorption of radiation and a wide range high photostability, which makes ZnO a favorite multi-purpose material [2,3,4,5,6]. Due to its unique optical and electrical properties, it is a widely used material in electronic applications, optoelectronic applications, and laser technology. Among the nanoscale metal oxides, ZnO has been widely used as an antimicrobial and antitumor agent [7]. Because of its blocking and absorbing properties, ZnO is included in some cosmetic lotions [8]. Following the sulfuric acid treatment process for zinc concentrate, zinc dust was added in order to autoclave the concentrate with 30% sulfuric acid [9]. ZnO nanoparticles have recently attracted attention due to their unique properties. ZnO nanoparticles have many promising applications in veterinary science due to their wound healing, antibacterial, antineoplastic, and antigenic properties. Recently, many research studies and experimental analyses have improved the effectiveness of zinc oxide (ZnO) materials, where each nano-size can be used to create nanowires, thin films, and other structures for intracellular pathogen protection and other applications. Reduced nanostructures were fabricated.

PURPOSE OF THE STUDY. A study of nanoparticulate zinc oxide materials and their potential applications based on indigenous raw material sources: progress, challenges, and prospects.

CHEMICAL METHODS FOR SYNTHESIS OF ZINC OXIDE NANOPARTICLES.

For the chemical synthesis of ZnO nanoparticles, several precursors and various conditions such as temperature, time, concentration of reactants, etc. can be used. These chemical methods allow better control of the morphology in terms of size and geometry due to the use of different parameters mentioned above [10]. (Figure 1) is fully explained.

Figure 1. Different strategies for the production of nanoparticulate zinc oxide.

ZnO NPs can be chemically synthesized using the following methods: mechanochemical process, controlled precipitation, sol-gel method, vapor transport method, solvothermal and hydrothermal methods media.

MECHANOCHEMICAL PROCESS.

In the mechanochemical process, the starting materials are the reactants, which are subjected to high-energy dry milling in a ball mill under the influence of ball-dust, at low temperatures. Diluent, a by-product of the reaction, accompanies the starting materials during the procedure [11,12]. Diluent acts as a reaction medium and affects the separation of nanoparticles, thereby limiting them. This, in turn, will prevent serious agglomeration. The starting materials that are traditionally used in this method are mainly anhydrous $ZnCl_2$, Na_2CO_3 synthesized ZnO NPs using the reaction between $ZnCl_2$ and Na_2CO_3 as diluent [13]. Pure nanocrystalline ZnO was obtained and dried in a drying oven. TEM images showed aggregated ZnO nanoparticles with an average size of less than 100 nm prepared by milling for 6 h followed by thermal treatment at 600 °C for 2 h. The effects of milling time and annealing were carefully investigated in this study. A decrease in nanocrystalline size from 25 nm to 21.5 nm was observed as the milling time increased from 2 h to 6 h where it reached stability. This phenomenon was chalked up to the dominant critical impact of the milling course. However, it was found that the crystal size increases with a sharp increase in temperature above 600 °C.

The activation energies for the growth of nano crystallites in different temperature ranges were calculated using Scott's equation. The activation energy for the growth was found to be 3.99 from 400 to 600 °C, it reached 20.75 kJ mol⁻¹. ZnO NPs were also prepared by a mechanochemical method using $ZnCl_2$ and Na_2CO_3 as starting materials [14]. $ZnCO_3$ was thermally treated at 400 °C. which caused it to decompose into ZnO. Meanwhile, the surface area of the ZnO nanopowder was evaluated. ZnO NPs synthesized by mechanochemical methods and using $ZnCl_2$ were obtained [15]. As a result of the reduction of the proposed work, the optical properties were improved and the ZnO NPs were obtained due to the improvement of the ratio of particle size to surface area [16]. The main disadvantage of the process is its presence. The main problem facing the unit is powder grinding and controlled minimization of particles of the required size. Note that the particle size decreases with increasing milling time and intensity. However, if the powder is exposed to milling for a longer period, the chance of contamination increases.

In addition to the advantages of this method, it is formed at a significantly lower cost with a decrease in particle agglomeration, and a clear homogeneous crystallite morphology and architecture. The mechanochemical process is especially optimal for the large-scale production of ZnO NPs.

CONTROLLED PRECIPITATION.

Controlled precipitation enabled the large-scale generation of nanoparticles in powder form for industrial use with reproducible properties. The method includes two steps: (a) precipitation of the precursor of ZnO from solution and (b) thermal treatment with subsequent milling for physical stimulation, the breakdown of calcined agglomerates of this precursor and the removal of impurities. A variety of methods can be used to precipitate ZnO by controlling several limiting factors, including reaction temperature, pH conditions, duration of precipitation, and the medium used for leaching. Using $ZnSO_4$ and NH_4OH [17]. Prepared nano-ZnO flakes. ZnO flakes confirmed by nanoscale SEM analysis were obtained. XRD analyses revealed the highly crystalline and 6-diameter angular structure of ZnO [18]. The precipitated white powder was

separated, then washed three times with deionized water and dried overnight at room temperature under dust-free conditions.

The hexagonal cross-section with the twin structure was 1.2 to 1.5 mm in diameter, and the aspect ratio was slightly smaller than 1:1. A new well-defined rice-like morphology of ZnO appeared when 0.1 M TEA was substituted with 0.01 M SDS in the reaction solution. Its diameters were similar to those of the walnut-shaped ZnO crystals, while the aspect ratio was slightly larger than 1:1. The precipitation method is a simple method. High quality defines the manufacturing method [19].

SOL-GEL METHOD.

The synthesis of ZnO NPs by the sol-gel method has recently been widely used. Its convenience, strength, robustness, reproducibility, and relatively mild conditions have led to its widespread use in the production of metal-oxide nanoparticles. This method facilitates the surface modification of zinc oxide with selected organic substances, thereby changing its characteristics and expanding the scope of its attributes and applications [20]. Zn(CH₃COO)₂·2H₂O, using polyvinyl pyrrolidone (PVP) and NaOH nano-structured. ZnO-prepared crystallites by the sol-gel method XRD characterization revealed a wurtzite structure with an average crystallite size of about 45 nm. The role morphology of PVP at different concentrations was investigated. Rod-like platelets with increasing PVP concentration. TEM images revealed the platelet-like grain size of ZnO, with a diameter of 150 nm for rod-shaped ZnO similarly designated as 100 nm [21]. Zinc oxide was synthesized based on the sol-gel method. Oxalic acid was used to form ZnO nanopowder with ethanol as a solvent showing the hexagonal wurtzite structure. SEM micrographs confirmed the formation of uniform, spherical ZnO nanoparticles. BET analysis determined a surface area of 10 m² g⁻¹. ZnO NPs with antibacterial properties were obtained [22]. Characteristics using the sol-gel method. Zinc acetate, oxalic acid, and water were used as raw materials in this process. A white gel precipitate was obtained first. Then it was thermally treated at 87 °C for 5 hours, then at 600 °C for 2 hours. ZnO NPs showed high crystallinity according to XRD data. 2 mm diameter SEM analysis for ZnO nano-aggregates from [23]. nano-structured ZnO crystallites were obtained using the sol-gel method. XRD examination and average value of basal diameter of cylinder-shaped crystallites and height of crystallites was 25-30 nm and 35-45 nm. The sol-gel method has several advantages compared to the above-mentioned methods. Among its primary advantages are the low cost of hardware and raw materials, reproducibility, and flexibility of manufacturing nanoparticles [24].

VAPOUR TRANSPORT METHOD.

In this process, zinc and oxygen or oxygen mixture vapors are transported and can react with each other resulting in the formation of ZnO nanoparticles. Due to the easy controllability of the vapor carrier, special attention has been paid to the method of ZnO morphology and crystal structures and nanostructures by changing the gas, substrate temperature, and substrate materials [25].

ZnO nanoparticles were also prepared on Au-coated Si using water vapor and oxygen gas. The advantage of using Au catalyst is its fast growth rate due to the catalytic effect of Au, an oxide material, but the main disadvantage is the residues of Au catalyst, which possible.

It affects the purity of ZnO nanostructures. Substrates were prepared by depositing a 200 nm thick layer of Au film using RF sputtering (JC500-3/D) from Au target on cleaned Si (100) wafers. The synthesis process involved the following steps: (a) passing Ar gas through a quartz

tube for 0.5 h to remove air; (b) increasing the furnace temperature to 800 °C with Ar gas flow; (c) maintaining the temperature at 800 C for 1 h and replacing Ar with Ar/H₂O vapor or Ar/O₂ gas mixture, the quartz tube pressure is maintained at 0.03-0.05 MPa; (d) turning off the oven and cooling the sample to RT at a rate of 7 °C per minute.

Vapor deposition method by thermal evaporation of Zn powder in the presence of O₂ gas. ZnO nanorods and nanoneedles are synthesized along the c-axis growth direction to form a hexagonal crystal structure. High-quality and well-oriented one-dimensional ZnO nanostructures were achieved as a function of changing diameter and growth rate.

Temperature and growth time. At 450 °C, ZnO nanorods were uniformly distributed across the substrate at a high density and had small average diameters. The diameter and length of the obtained nanorods were in the range of 19-27 nm and 2.8 mm, respectively. The temperature increased to 550 °C, and the ZnO nanorods grew perpendicular to the substrate, with a uniform length across them, and a more consistent shape and size with a width of approximately 85 nm and a length of 3.8 mm. The morphological change and distribution occurred at a growth temperature of 650 °C and hexagonal ZnO nanorods.

Each was observed to be 95 nm at the tip and 900 nm in length. The growth mechanism of 1D ZnO was used in the study as a Cu metal catalyst. The presented nanostructures were based on the VLS method.

This method can be divided into three stages as follows: the first, Zn vapor and catalytic Cu formed liquid alloy drops during heating at a certain temperature, which represents the initial stage of the nucleation process. Second, the crystal nuclei act as nucleation sites on the substrate until supersaturation is reached, resulting from the adsorption of gaseous species, and the resulting sites are no longer in service. Finally, the axial growth of nanorods started from these sites [26]. In the presence of different Cu metal catalysts, the mechanism according to the growth temperature and nucleation theory is the VLS growth mechanism, the Cu catalyst nanoclusters are formed due to capillarity, which leads to the beading of the Cu layer at high growth temperatures. As a result, the Cu–Zn alloy reached a certain solubility depending on the temperature; then, Zn vapors began to deposit at the interface between the surface and the droplet. This, in turn, determined the diameter and size of the nanostructures according to the size of the liquid alloy droplets. Especially large amounts of ZnO nanorods with lower diameters were formed at lower growth rates at 450 °C. Zn metal powder (melting point 419 °C) at 450 °C had a sufficiently high vapor pressure to inhibit the growth of ZnO nanorods on the glass substrate. Study the VLS method and as a result, the decrease in the growth temperature with the reduction of Zn vapor.

In addition, the consumption of Zn vapor during the growth period along with high growth temperature, the diameter of nanorods decreased significantly. As a result, this condition led to the production of typical hierarchical rods.

ZnO nanorods with a diameter of 19–27 nm and a length of 2.8 mm were obtained during the growth time of 30 min. When the growth time increased to 45 minutes, nanoneedles appeared. The needles showed an average diameter of 65-190 nm and a length of 3.2 mm. On the other hand, nanoneedles are grown for 60 minutes with a diameter of approximately 80-250 nm and a length of 3.8 mm [27]. They developed a flexible light-emitting nanocomposite based on ZnO nanotetrapods (NTPs).

HYDROTHERMAL METHOD.

The hydrothermal method is an easy-to-use method for producing nanoparticles. This method of chemical synthesis has the distinct advantage of being a harmless environment. The mixed substrates are placed in an autoclave and then slowly heated to a temperature of 100-300 °C. The heating is continued for some time and then cooling is observed. This leads to the formation of crystal nuclei, and then to the growth of nuclei.

A 1:2 mixture of ZnCl₂ and NaOH in aqueous medium was [28]. A white Zn(OH)₂ precipitate was formed and ZnO NPs were formed by hydrothermal treatment. XRD and TEM tests were conducted to determine the average size and morphology of the ZnO NPs thus formed. Two factors, namely temperature and reaction time, were found to have a significant effect on the size and architecture of ZnO NPs. With increasing temperature, it was found that the morphology of the particle changes from looking like a polyhedral rod. In addition, a significant increase in crystallinity and elongation of particle size was noted as a disadvantage of the procedure with pH [29]. The NPs thus formed had a hexagonal wurtzite structure. XRD

The analysis showed an increase in the average grain size with increased temperature and concentration of substrates. The average grain size of ZnO NPs prepared from 0.3 M NaOH was found to increase from 7 to 7 using 6 h growth time and 16 nm with increasing temperature from 100 to 200 °C. On average, the grain size of ZnO synthesized at 200 °C for 12 hours increases from 12 to 24 nm with increasing concentration of NaOH from 0.2 M to 0.5 M. This process has many advantages compared to other methods. Organic solvents are not used in this procedure [30].

SOLVOTHERMAL METHOD.

The main goal of using the solvothermal technique is to create a wide range of nanostructured metal oxides with a large surface area, significant crystallinity and excellent thermal stability. Thermal decomposition of organometallic compounds in organic media is the basis of this procedure [31].

ZnO was produced with several morphologies-nanoneedles, nanorods and nanowires-obtained under different solvothermal conditions.

Precursors with ZnO nanoparticles and heat treatment at 180 °C for 72 hours, nanoneedles with a diameter of 450-900 nm, a length of 8-20 nm, and a ratio of 0.05. With ZnO nanoparticles and stearic acid as precursors and 180 C thermal, nanorods with a diameter of 40–160 nm, a length of 5–8 nm, and an aspect ratio of 0.014 were realized for 168 h.

Formed. With ZnO (stearic acid) as a 0.38 nanocomposite as a precursor and heat treatment at 180 °C for 168 hours, nanowires with a diameter of 30–50 nm, a length of 0.8–1 nm and an aspect ratio of 0.04 were formed [32]. Also used a solvothermal route to form ZnO. The most important of them is that reactions can be carried out under defined conditions.

MODIFICATIONS.

Some characteristics of the product, such as size, and structure, can be changed by morphology, color, hardness, softness and firmness. The modification can improve the compatibility of ZnO-NPs with organic (carboxylic acid, silanes), inorganic (metal oxides);

and polymers, etc. (Figure 2), which improves ZnO-NP performance properties, consumption time, life cycle, and optical properties, and also makes it more useful to obtain more benefits and significantly reduce defects [33-36]. Thus, the modification techniques described in various potential ZnO-NPs publications are included in this section as outlined below.

Figure 2. Schematic diagram of the most popular methods of ZnO modification

The modification of ZnO particles found a practical answer to the agglomeration problem. Photocatalytic activity of the inorganic component (silicon oxide) on the ZnO surface decreases; but organic molecules increased the compatibility of ZnO with the organic matrix. When using these modifiers, the surface was explored as a highly transparent, transparent material to promote the significant benefits of modified ZnO.

UV protection. The underlying mechanisms and influencing factors of ZnO-NPs anti-yeast and anti-water effects have been investigated [37-38].

POTENTIAL APPLICATIONS.

In recent years, ZnO NPs have witnessed a dramatic increase in research interest due to their unique properties to achieve widespread applications in transparent electronics, ultraviolet (UV) light emitters, piezoelectric devices, chemical sensors, optoelectronics, solar cells, and spin electronics [39]. Since ZnO is non-toxic, it has recently been widely used as an excellent photocatalyst for the degradation of many emerging organic pollutants. (Figure 3). Several of these applications of ZnO NPs are listed below.

Figure 3. Application of zinc oxide NPs.

ZnO is also of great interest as a raw material in existing pharmaceuticals and as a cosmetic, paint, concrete, and pigment [40]. It is widely used as a UV filter in the rubber industry, products, textile industry, and medical and biological industry.

CONCLUSION

This overview of ZnO is to demonstrate the various strategies adopted to fabricate ZnO nanostructures and their wide range of applications. In addition, a holistic picture of the future prospects of nano-structured ZnO is shown in its applications in the discussed areas.

A material that exhibits diverse properties, functionality, and applications in the emerging field of nanotechnology. High chemical stability, high photostability, a wide range of radiation absorption, biodegradability and biocompatibility provide ZnO. NPs are used in new materials and potential applications in a wide range of technology areas. In addition, various environmentally friendly bio-mediated syntheses of ZnO particles appear. They have improved features that can be used better.

The application of the technology in various fields has attracted more attention and interest in the research world. The optoelectronic properties of ZnO NPs are widely used in the fabrication of ZnO-based electron transport layers in dye-sensitized solar cells and perovskite solar cells.

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